

BEAGLE
BLUE OCEANS STRATEGY
FOR VALUE CREATION

D1.4 Data Management Plan

June 2024

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Abstract:	Beyond research publications, BEAGLE, will generate and collect a rich variety and considerable amount of data and research outputs, which will be managed in line with the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) principles, as per requirements of the Horizon Europe legal provisions. The FAIR principles will apply from the start point of the project and will be maintained beyond its end. BEAGLE will tackle the data management, from month 1, through a specific plan named BEAGLE Data Management Plan (BDMP). The Project Manager will deliver at month 6 the first version of BDMP, and a final one at month 36. The research data and other outputs and metadata will be collected from the scientific literature but also from the implementing experience of the participating partners in the project, both as beneficiaries and project collaborators.

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Table 1: Expected datasets generated by BEAGLE

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List of Abbreviations and Acronyms	
A-I	Academia-Industry
BEAGLE	Blue Oceans Strategy for Value Creation
BDMP	BEAGLE Data Management Plan
C	Call for Proposal
CA	Consortium Agreement
CSA	Coordination and Support Actions
D	Deliverable
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DoA	Description of Action
DPC	Data Protection Coordinator
DPO	Data Protection Officer
EU	European Union
EC	European Commission
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FAIR	FAIR principle for open data: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
JSON-LD	JSON format for Linking Data
RDA	Research Data Alliance
RDF	Resource Description Framework
RDR	Research Data Repository
T	Task
WP	Work Package

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document is dedicated to the BEAGLE Data Management Plan (BDMP). The objective is to outline how the research data collected or generated will be managed during the course of the BEAGLE project over the span of 3 years. It adheres to the template provided by the European Commission on the Participant Portal.

The BDMP establishes a comprehensive framework for managing data across the project, integrating the principles outlined under the FAIR Data Approach and GDPR compliance. It elaborates on various aspects such as purpose of data collection, types and formats of data, re-usage of existing data, origin of data, utility of data and the incorporation of open innovation and open science practices. The plan emphasizes efficient resource allocation and robust data security to ensure data is managed in compliance with ethical standards, legal requirements, and intellectual property rights (IPR), facilitating their accessibility and reusability by the broader community.

1 DATA MANAGEMENT FRAMEWORK

1.1 PURPOSE OF THE BEAGLE DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN (BDMP)

The BEAGLE project is an EU-funded initiative under Horizon Europe Research with the objective of proving the enhancement of productivity and efficiency of the Knowledge valorisation and value creation processes in the area of Academia-Industry (A-I) linkages across the European innovation ecosystem through a co-creation experiment based on the Blue Oceans Strategy.

The BEAGLE Data Management Plan (BDMP) will outline the data that the project will collect or generate, the data to be shared or made available, and the methods of data description. It will identify the relevant data protection laws and regulations at both EU and national levels that need to be adhered to, and describe the methodologies to safeguard data. As part of a European initiative, BEAGLE will set out guidelines to ensure that research data adhere to the FAIR principles—making data findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable.

The dissemination level of this Deliverable 1.4 is designated as 'PUBLIC' (PU). URV, as the leader of Work Package 1 (WP1), is responsible for it and serves as its main contributor with support from all consortium partners. CTAG have been appointed as peer reviewers for D1.4. It represents the initial version, delivered in Month 6 of the project, and will be updated throughout the project's lifecycle.

1.2 EXPECTED DATASETS GENERATED BY BEAGLE

Dataset name and outline of data	Institutions in charge	WP
BEAGLE_PartnerMemberInfo_v1.0 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Member names - Organization details - Contact information - Roles and responsibilities - Contributions to the project - Communication and dissemination materials 	URV F6S	WP1 WP6
BEAGLE_BestPracticeMapping_v1.0 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Survey responses - Identified best practices - Analysis and mapping results - Regional comparisons - Implementation guidelines - Feedback forms from events and meetings - Best practices documentation (case studies, white papers, research articles, reports, recorded interviews or webinars with experts) 	CTAG F6S	WP2
BEAGLE_IndustryOpenCall_v1.0 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Open call announcements - Applicant details - Collected demands - Evaluation criteria - Selected proposals - Video fact sheets (video content descriptions, viewing statistics, stakeholder feedback) 	CTAG CTBG	WP2 and WP3
BEAGLE_IndustryStakeholderDemand_v1.0 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Stakeholder details 	CTAG CTBG	WP2 and WP3

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Demand descriptions - Potential collaboration opportunities - Feedback and requirements - Insights and ideas from stakeholders (collected through workshops) 		
<p>BEAGLE_AcademicOpenCall_v1.0</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Open call announcements - Applicant details - Offerings descriptions - Evaluation criteria - Selected proposals - Video fact sheets (video content descriptions, viewing statistics, stakeholder feedback) 	<p>UWB URV</p>	<p>WP4</p>
<p>BEAGLE_AcademicStakeholderOffer_v1.0</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Stakeholder details - Offer descriptions - Collaboration opportunities - Feedback and contributions - Detailed stakeholder information (contact details, areas of expertise, research interests, past collaborations) 	<p>UWB URV</p>	<p>WP4</p>
<p>BEAGLE_MixedTeamExperiment_v1.0</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Team member details - Experimental design - Collaboration dynamics - Experiment results - Analysis and findings 	<p>URV CTAG</p>	<p>WP5</p>

Table 1: Expected datasets generated by BEAGLE.

1.3 DATA SUMMARY

1.3.1 PURPOSE OF THE DATA COLLECTION/GENERATION

The purpose of data collection and generation in BEAGLE is to identify and analyse emerging market opportunities, facilitate co-creation activities, and develop innovative solutions. This involves gathering insights from various sources such as workshops, surveys, interviews, video-factsheets and system innovation approaches to uncover new market niches and potential blue ocean opportunities. By systematically collecting and analysing data, BEAGLE aims to inform decision-making processes, guide the co-creation of innovation proposals, and ultimately contribute to the development of 12 new innovative market niches.

BEAGLE project is expected to collect/generate data from:

- Workshops: To determine stakeholders’ understanding, acceptability and engagement with our framework in Blue Ocean, BEAGLE will organize workshops to engage participants and gather their insights and ideas. These workshops will also provide event and networking data, including event schedules and agendas, attendee lists and profiles, as well as feedback and evaluations from past events.
- Surveys: The project will design and distribute surveys to collect diverse viewpoints and feedback, aiding in the identification of potential market opportunities. Within WP2, the project will use the EU Survey as a trusted tool to collect data. This approach helps to identify best practices in knowledge valorisation networks. Additionally, surveys will gather insights from stakeholders on best practices and market needs, and feedback forms from events and meetings will be collected to inform future efforts. To further support this, best practices documentation will be compiled, including case studies of successful knowledge valorisation, white papers, research articles, and reports, as well as recorded interviews or webinars with experts.

- Interviews: Through face-to-face or remote interviews with stakeholders, the project can gain deeper understanding of their needs, challenges, and visions. Additionally, the project will gather detailed stakeholder information, including contact details, areas of expertise, research interests, and past collaborations from academia; contact details, industry sectors, innovation interests, and past collaborations from industry; and profiles, experience, and networks from facilitators. This comprehensive approach will ensure that the project is well-informed and able to address the diverse requirements and opportunities within its scope.
- Video-factsheets: Video materials containing information about different market sectors and innovation opportunities will be collected and analysed.
- System innovation approaches: Using system innovation methods such as system dynamics modelling or systems analysis to understand interactions and impacts between different market sectors, discovering new market opportunities.

1.3.2 TYPES AND FORMATS OF DATA GENERATED/COLLECTED

This version of the BDMP does not yet compile all metadata related to the data produced in the BEAGLE project. However, several domains within the project already adhere to various rules and recommendations. This initial identification of standards includes:

- Microsoft Office file format will be the reference for documents, spreadsheets and presentations. Text-based documents will primarily use Microsoft Word (.doc, .docx), with spreadsheets (.xls, .xlsx) and presentations (.ppt, .pptx). For handling larger datasets, .csv and .txt formats will be used. All finalized and approved documents will also be available as .pdf files.
- For illustrations and graphic design, Microsoft Visio (.vsd), Adobe Photoshop (various formats, mostly .png), will be utilized, with outputs available in .jpg, .psd, .tiff, and .ai formats.
- Audio files will be in MP3 or WAV formats.
- Video files will be in Quicktime Movie or Windows Media Video formats.
- For statistical purposes, other formats include .sas7bdat (SAS), .RData (R), .SAV (SPSS), .mat (matlab).
- Where applicable data formats may be migrated when new technologies become available and are proved robust enough to ensure digital continuity and continued availability of data.

These file formats are selected for their wide acceptance and standardization. Files will be converted to open formats wherever feasible for long-term preservation.

Metadata will be organized using Resource Description Framework (RDF) or JSON-LD (JSON format for linking data) formats using the FAIR Data Point vocabulary. These metadata formats are chosen to provide a comprehensive explanation of the data and ensure compatibility with international standards.

1.3.3 RE-USAGE OF EXISTING DATA

BEAGLE will incorporate existing datasets that are relevant to its research focus. These datasets may include public databases, previous research results, and data from other related projects. The reuse of such data allows for a broader and more comprehensive analysis by integrating well-established findings and datasets.

Furthermore, it is not projected to share data with EU and non-EU members who are not part of the consortium.

1.3.4 ORIGIN/PROVENANCE OF THE DATA, EITHER GENERATED OR RE-USED

At the current state of the project, data will be gathered from:

- Data from sign-up sheets, event schedules, agendas, attendee lists, profiles, feedback, and evaluations at workshops
- Data submitted to surveys, including market opportunities identification, case studies, white papers, research articles, reports, and recorded interviews or webinars with experts.

- Data from interviews
- Personal data upon requests of the consortium
- Data collected from video fact sheets.
- Insights and ideas from stakeholders collected through workshops.
- Stakeholder details and potential collaboration opportunities from industry stakeholder demand collection
- System dynamics modelling and systems analysis from system innovation approaches.

All data, whether generated or re-used, will be thoroughly documented to include details about its origin, the methods used for its collection or generation, and any processing steps involved. Each partner institution will be the owner of the data that will be collected. This includes metadata documentation, ensuring that proper documentation and adherence to open standards are maintained. Such practices are essential to maintain data quality, reproducibility, and transparency, thereby facilitating future reuse and validation by other researchers and stakeholders.

1.3.5 DATA UTILITY

The datasets generated and collected throughout the BEAGLE project are crucial for enhancing project outcomes and ensuring broad benefits. They provide valuable insights into stakeholder engagement, market opportunities, best practices, and knowledge valorisation. By leveraging data from workshops, surveys, interviews, video fact sheets, and system innovation approaches, the project can refine strategies, validate methodologies, and discover new opportunities. This comprehensive data utilization supports academic-industry collaboration and fosters disruptive innovation, aligning with the principles of the Blue Ocean Strategy. Ultimately, these efforts ensure that the project remains well-informed and can effectively address diverse requirements, contributing to the successful achievement of its objectives and creating significant impact in the targeted sectors.

1.4 IPR COMMITMENTS IN BEAGLE

The IPR issue was described in the Grant Agreement (GA) indicating that the baseline of the negotiation of the corresponding Consortium Agreement (CA) clause will be served as the default rules for the IPR of Horizon Europe Framework. After consulting with all partners, no partner stated for bringing any background neither any foreground is expected to be created during the span life of the project. In this case, if any partner or participant in Task 5.2 and/or Task 5.3 generate or create any IPR, such IPR will be formed as a bilateral agreement between the joint owners, which is not within the framework of BEAGLE. BEAGLE only creates the space and framework to promote the connection. Therefore, no IPR is foreseen within the BEAGLE project execution, which implies that IPR issues are not applied to BEAGLE.

1.5 OPEN INNOVATION AND OPEN SCIENCE PRACTICES WITHIN BEAGLE

The BDMP will adhere to Article 17 of the Model GA, which requires project participants to store their data in a research data repository and ensure that it is accessible to third parties. Such access should include the ability to access, mine, exploit, reproduce, and disseminate the data, which will also aid in validating the results presented in scientific publications. Additionally, Article 17 stipulates that participants must provide information about the tools and instruments necessary for validating project outcomes via the repository.

- Open Sharing, Connecting, and Exchanging Digital Platforms: BEAGLE will use an existing digital full operating website to interconnect all consortium partners, including clusters' associates (companies), individual business managers, universities' research groups, and individual researchers. The virtual website is designed to act as a focal point for sharing bottom-up co-identified industry challenges and needs by Mixed Teams as outlined in **WP3** and **WP4**. When permitted by the participants, the website will also share the innovation expectations of individual companies. This

open sharing and connecting approach will enhance collaboration, foster innovation, and address industry needs effectively, ensuring the project's objectives are met and creating significant impact.

- Early and open sharing: The URV project manager, as **WP1** leader too, will supervise that all BEAGLE partners will share as soon as possible all the outputs and methodologies achieved during the project implementation with the aim to enable and enhance their reproducibility. Preregistration and preprints platforms, such as Zenodo and SocArXiv, respectively, will be used to increase transparency and credibility.
- Research data management: The BDMP will be, as well as the early open sharing practices, supervised and performed by the **WP1** leader. All the data collection, organisation, curation, storage, (long-term) preservation, security, quality assurance and other related activities will be planned in the BDMP, which will follow the FAIR principles. See next section 2 for more detail.
- Open access: **WP6** is the one devoted to the dissemination of the results. As the leader of **WP6**, F6S will ensure Open Access by publishing and assisting all partners in publishing in open peer-reviewed scientific journals and depositing in a trusted repository, at the time of publication or before through pre-prints, under a CC BY (or equivalent) license. It will be informed via the repository any research output or other instruments needed to validate the scientific conclusions (mainly Zenodo and SocArXiv, as previously mentioned).
- Citizen, civil society, and end-user engagement: Again, these practices and activities will be carried out into the **WP6**. However, all implementing partners, will assume citizenship and end-user engagement through the co-creation of the innovative projects that will grow from the activities developed within **WP5**.

1.6 GDPR COMPLIANCE

BEAGLE upholds stringent GDPR compliance to protect personal data, including sensitive data, in its project activities. Consequently, the consortium will implement necessary measures to protect participants' privacy. All participants will be informed about the data collection process, the type of data collected, its intended use, and their rights under the project. The project will adhere to the data protection laws of the European Union (Regulation (EU) 2016/679) as well as the local laws of each partner involved.

BEAGLE aims to minimize the use of personal data, limiting it only to what is necessary to accomplish project objectives and relying heavily on mechanisms that protect participants, such as anonymization and data aggregation. This approach minimizes the risk to individual rights and facilitates the use of data for academic research.

The project employs advanced data protection measures, conducts regular audits, and ensures that data handling practices respect participants' rights to privacy.

In terms of data collection, BEAGLE is committed to honesty and transparency. It ensures that all participants provide free and informed consent. No personal information will be disseminated without prior written consent from the individuals involved.

Before any project activity begins, all participants will receive detailed information about the activity and data usage, and they will provide written consent confirming their understanding and agreement.

- For the BEAGLE Open call, users joining the community will consent to data usage and management as outlined upon joining.
- For on-site activities or instances where users have not previously consented via the Open call, an alternative process is in place. An informed consent form (available in English) has been prepared (see Annex I), which includes a detailed explanation of the activity, data usage, and terms, followed by a section where users consent to these terms and to the processing of data and image rights.

No user will participate in any project activities without having read, understood, and given their consent.

2 FAIR DATA APPROACH

Beyond research publications, BEAGLE, will generate and collect a rich variety and considerable amount of data and research outputs, which will be managed in line with the FAIR principles, as per requirements of the Horizon Europe legal provisions. The FAIR principles will apply from the start point of the project and will be maintained beyond its end. BEAGLE will tackle the data management, from month 1, through a specific plan named BEAGLE Data Management Plan (BDMP). The Project Manager URV will deliver at month 6 the first version of BDMP, and a final one at month 36. The research data and other outputs and metadata will be collected from the scientific literature but also from the implementing experience of the participating partners in the project, both as beneficiaries and project collaborators. As the acronym FAIR describes, the following aspects will be addressed: Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, Reusability

2.1 MAKING DATA FINDABLE

To facilitate the distinction and identification of datasets, each will be assigned a unique name, which will also serve as its identifier. The principle regarding globally unique and persistent identifiers will be followed. The records will be named consistently, logically and in a predictable way, and will also ensure similar records can be distinguished from one another.

The following naming conventions will be followed:

- Folders will be ordered hierarchically and will be clearly named.
- All data files produced, including emails, will be labelled with the term "BEAGLE," followed by the Deliverable number, followed by a filename that briefly describes its content, a version number (or the term "FINAL"), and, if relevant, the abbreviation of the organization that prepared the document. Additionally, each dataset collected, processed, or generated within the project will include a brief description.

Example:

File Naming Convention:

BEAGLE_D1.4 DMP_v0.0_URV

BEAGLE_D2.4 Marketplace_FINAL_F6S

Dataset Description:

Dataset Name: BEAGLE_SurveyData_v1.0

Description: This dataset contains the responses from the initial project survey conducted during February-May 2024. The survey aimed to gather baseline data on best practices in knowledge valorisation in Europe. This includes initiatives, programmes, and instruments used for knowledge valorisation, which open new channels of value innovation, reshaping mature sectors and promoting sustainable growth through blue ocean strategy.

Regarding the approach versioning, clear version numbers and dates will be provided, although it is anticipated that only one version of each dataset will be deposited at the end of the project.

BEAGLE will store retrospective (re-use data, if any) and prospective (collected) research data in centralized institutional repository, COARA, which is a federated and multidisciplinary Research Data Repository (RDR) that allows Catalan universities (including URV), CERCA research centres, and other research entities to publish research datasets in a FAIR manner, following European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) guidelines. This repository will be architected to leverage rich metadata (e.g., technical, operational, and business metadata), integrating with existing metadata tools. This gives the ability to understand lineage, quality, and lifecycle, and provides crucial visibility into this data-rich environment.

For further data storage, sharing and management, we will consider trusted repositories such as Zenodo and SocArXiv as the primary options. Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org>), the repository created by CERN under OpenAIRE, will be used by default. A specific section linked to the project will be created within Zenodo. Additionally, the data will also be available in SocArXiv. The data/research outputs from BEAGLE will be stored and appropriately catalogued in these repositories.

File names will have descriptive titles to be easily found, and unique identifiers will be used by all partners. Metadata on FAIR Data Points will be used for indexing by search engines. Where possible, standard vocabulary will be used to assist with keyword searches. Keywords will identify the data and make it easily searchable using standard terminology.

Additionally, we will consider the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), which allocates a persistent digital object identifier (DOI) to the data. This ensures that our data follows the FAIR principles, providing crucial visibility into this data-rich environment.

In the absence of specific metadata standards in our discipline, we will create custom metadata that includes technical specifications, data collection methods, processing protocols, and contextual information to ensure data usability and reproducibility.

2.2 MAKING DATA ACCESSIBLE

BEAGLE will use Microsoft Teams Repository to share data, knowledge and documents among project partners. Each partner will be responsible for implementing the appropriate mechanisms for dealing with the data to be shared. All data that must be shared between BEAGLE partners containing sensitive data will be properly anonymised. To ensure secure and reliable data storage and management, this project plans to use Zenodo as the platform for data storage and management, COARA for sharing research datasets in a FAIR manner, and SocArXiv for linking databases and publications. Furthermore, the open results will be disseminated through the BEAGLE project website (<https://projectbeagle.eu/>), and various social media channels.

The framework for capturing and managing the BEAGLE data platform's rich metadata will be essential for democratising access to the data and maximising the value of the data platform. The metadata will also enable data governance, which consists of policies and standards for the management, quality, and use of data, all critical for managing data and securing access. To access the data, free and open protocols such as HTTP/HTTPS will be used. Detailed conditions under which data are accessible will be provided. Generated data during the project will be published in trusted and reputable repositories and peer-reviewed journals.

Appropriate arrangements with Zenodo and SocArXiv have been explored to ensure seamless data deposition and management. Zenodo ensures that each dataset is assigned a unique identifier (DOI). Additionally, COARA will facilitate the sharing of research datasets in a FAIR manner. Once the data is deposited, URV's CRAI staff will curate and review the data, and a notification email will be sent with the results.

2.2.1 REPOSITORY

The use of the mentioned repositories will make possible keeping available the data afterwards, adhering to OpenAire guidelines in Horizon Europe (<https://www.openaire.eu/horizon-europe>), and thus to the EU Commission, Open access & Data management guidelines, following the principle "as open as possible as closed as necessary", such as EOSC. The used repositories will be included in registries of scientific repositories. Likewise, BEAGLE will support the publication of data in open data portals, i.e., portals that operate in national, regional, or EU data portals (e.g., <https://open-data.europa.eu/en/data>).

Zenodo serves as a primary repository for all project outputs, including datasets, publications, and other research materials. Zenodo not only facilitates open access to research results but also ensures that each piece of data is accompanied by a DOI to enhance its discoverability and citation. The Zenodo community adheres to strict access controls and metadata standards to ensure data is both secure and aligned with FAIR principles. SocArXiv, an open archive for social science research, complements Zenodo by offering a platform specifically tailored to social sciences. It supports the sharing and dissemination of research outputs, ensuring they are accessible to a broad audience. SocArXiv integrates with other repositories and adheres to similar metadata and access standards, promoting transparency and collaboration in social science research.

OpenAIRE serves as a central hub for the European Open Science ecosystem, providing support for researchers, funders, and institutions in adopting and implementing Open Science practices. Much like Zenodo, OpenAIRE enhances the visibility and accessibility of research results but extends its capabilities to include a comprehensive suite of services that support the entire lifecycle of research dissemination and compliance with Open Access mandates. OpenAIRE offers other tools like Argos for data processing and Zenodo for data publishing, tools that are encouraged to be used within BEAGLE.

COARA is used as institutional repository of URV for sharing research datasets in a FAIR manner. Detailed information about COARA, including how to create a user account and deposit data, can be found in the user guide. Once the data is deposited, URV's CRAI staff will curate and review the data, and a notification email will be sent with the results. For any questions or issues, direct assistance can be sought via repositori@urv.cat.

The only data that will not be openly available includes information containing personally identifiable details and data associated with confidential deliverables. Personal data handled in the project will not be publicly accessible but will remain closed and inaccessible to third parties. For the duration of the project, personal data will be stored on local secured server of the partner responsible of taking care of this.

2.2.2 DATA

Data will be released in standard file formats such as txt, pdf, csv, etc. Access to all data will be facilitated through standard tools. While relevant software for data access will be provided, it is not considered mandatory. Should it become necessary, we will furnish the necessary open-source tools for accessing and analysing the data.

To ensure compliance with the FAIR principles, we will make data accessible following the specified timelines for data collection. This section outlines the periods during which prospective data will be collected and describes the types of data collected in open calls for industry and academia.

Data description

1. Which data will be collected in Open call for the industry?

During the open call for industry, we will collect data that includes but is not limited to:

- Specific industry demands and challenges
- Market needs and innovation gaps
- Industry problem statements
- Desired technological advancements and improvements
- Video fact sheet (highlights industry demands, market needs, innovation gaps, problem statements, and desired technological advancements)

This data will be gathered through submissions from various industry stakeholders. The collected data will help in understanding current industry practices and identifying areas for improvement and innovation.

2. Which data will be collected in Open call for the academia?

During the open call for academia, we will collect data that includes but is not limited to:

- Research proposals and potential solutions
- Experimental and theoretical frameworks
- Previous research findings applicable to industry challenges
- Collaborative project ideas aimed at addressing industry demands
- Video fact sheet (summarizes research proposals, solutions, frameworks, applicable findings, and collaborative ideas)

Academic institutions, researchers, and scholars will be invited to submit their solutions and research proposals. This data collection aims to harness academic expertise to address the specific demands identified by the industry, fostering collaboration and innovation.

The following data will not be made publicly available:

- Data obtained with the permission of third parties, but the third parties have not agreed to make the data publicly available.
- Data that compromises the protection of a partner(s) intellectual property.
- Any participant data which cannot be fully anonymised.

If an embargo is applied to allow time for publication or protection of intellectual property, it will be specified along with the reason and duration of the embargo. Research data will be made available as soon as possible. Access to restricted data will be provided through controlled access protocols during and after the project, with detailed conditions for access outlined.

To ensure compliance with the FAIR principles, we will make data accessible following the specified timelines for data collection. The identity of individuals accessing the data will be verified through secure authentication methods. Generated data during the project will be published in trusted and reputable repositories and peer-reviewed journals. A data access committee will be established to evaluate and approve access requests to personal or sensitive data.

2.2.3 METADATA

RDF or JSON-LD formats using the FAIR Data Point vocabulary will be used to structure the metadata. The data will be uploaded to the repository in a non-proprietary format (.csv) and will be then deleted from the indicated BEAGLE repository data platform.

Metadata will be made openly available and licensed under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the GA. The metadata will include information necessary to enable users to access the data.

BEAGLE's archive will include the following information:

- Data content
 - All participant-related data
 - Project Metadata
 - Data export as .csv and .sql
- Resources
 - all CS-related files
- Documentation
 - Database documentation
 - Configuration files

The data will remain available and findable for a minimum of five years after the project's completion. Metadata will be guaranteed to remain available even after the data is no longer accessible. Documentation or references about any software needed to access or read the data will be included. Where possible, relevant software will be included, preferably as open-source code.

2.3 MAKING DATA INTEROPERABLE

Throughout the project, electronic records of data and metadata will be systematically generated and stored in standard formats. These records will be archived in institutional repositories of the participating entities and, where applicable, on their respective labs or units' websites. As the project advances and data accrues, strategies for enhancing data interoperability will be delineated in subsequent versions of the BDMP. We will follow recognized standards such as RDF, JSON-LD for metadata, and use common file formats like CSV, PDF, and SQL to ensure interoperability. We will follow community-endorsed best practices for data interoperability, including those recommended by the Research Data Alliance (RDA) and FAIR principles. Standard file formats will be utilized for all datasets, each accompanied by standard Zenodo metadata. The data generated is expected to exhibit a high degree of interoperability due to the use of common file formats such as reports and presentations. If it is unavoidable to use uncommon or project-specific ontologies or vocabularies, we will provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies

to ensure broader interoperability. Generated ontologies or vocabularies will be openly published to allow for reusing, refining, or extending by other researchers. Our data will include qualified references to other datasets from our project and relevant datasets from previous research to enhance context and reusability.

To ensure accessibility and international relevance, all published, and internally shared data will be presented in English. In cases where languages other than English are employed, such as in interviews with local stakeholders, transcripts or translations in English will be provided.

2.4 INCREASE DATA USE

The adopted strategies toward open access sharing in trusted and OpenAire-compliant repositories, with a strong focus on assignment of licenses toward data sharing and re-usability, together with the usage of data and metadata standards, will ease and promote the reusability of data outputs from BEAGLE. Access to this data will be free of charge, and no permission restriction will be placed on it. Documentation such as readme files, methodology descriptions, codebooks, data cleaning procedures, analyses, variable definitions, and units of measurement will be provided to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use.

Each partner responsible for generating data will ensure its quality in terms of content and formalities, such as eliminating outliers from numerical data and ensuring correct formatting, internal referencing, and use of images in project reports. Data quality is integral to the project's quality plan, Deliverable D1.3, with URV overseeing performance monitoring and ensuring procedural and result quality. The provenance of the data will be thoroughly documented using appropriate standards to ensure traceability and reliability. Further to the FAIR principles, the BDMP will also address research outputs other than data, carefully consider the allocation of resources, ensure data security, and address ethical aspects.

The ability to download the open-access data will be kept possible for a minimum of 5 years. However, the use of a permanent repository (with a DOI) as a long-term archive should guarantee the accessibility of these data for a minimum of 10 years from the end of the project.

3 ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES

Data management within the BEAGLE project will be conducted under WP1, with URV serving as the project coordinator responsible for overseeing these efforts. A portion of the overall budget and person-months from WP1 has been dedicated to these activities. Currently, the project coordinator is responsible for ensuring FAIR data management practices. The costs for making data FAIR include direct costs for storage and archiving, and indirect costs related to re-use and security. These will be covered by the Horizon Europe grant, provided they align with the conditions stipulated in the GA.

Expenses associated with providing open access to research data are considered eligible under the Horizon Europe grant, provided they align with the conditions stipulated in the GA. Issues related to the long-term preservation of data, associated costs, potential value, and strategies for data retention beyond the project's lifespan, as well as budget allocation for storage and archiving, will be addressed collectively by the consortium during the General Assembly meetings. To ensure long-term preservation, funds will be allocated to maintain the research data repository operational and accessible for a minimum of five years.

Without prejudice to the decisions made by the General Assembly, the coordinator of the BEAGLE project, URV, will allocate funds to maintain the research data repository operational and accessible for a minimum of five years following the conclusion of the project. These expenses will be incorporated into the Microsoft Office license fees of URV. This budgetary allocation ensures the long-term preservation and accessibility of research data, aligning with our commitment to uphold data integrity and availability as stipulated in the project's guidelines.

4 DATA SECURITY

In BEAGLE, data security is essential. The project implements comprehensive security measures including encrypted data storage, rigorous access controls, and regular security audits. An incident response plan provides a structured approach to managing data breaches, ensuring rapid response and mitigation of any potential impacts on data integrity and project operations.

BEAGLE utilizes a suite of tools and platforms to ensure data is securely stored, easily shared among consortium members, and protected from unauthorized access:

- **Secure Cloud Storage:** For the storage of sensitive data, secure, encrypted cloud services are used to ensure data integrity and security.
- **Collaborative Platforms:** Tools like Microsoft Teams Repository are employed to facilitate the sharing of documents and collaborative data analysis among project members.

To protect the data generated, used, or processed during the BEAGLE project, it is crucial to recognize potential threats, establish defensive layers, and engage in proactive management and protection measures throughout the project's lifecycle.

BEAGLE follows the five fundamental principles of information security¹ to ensure robust data protection: confidentiality, integrity, availability, authenticity, and non-repudiation.

- **Confidentiality:** Ensuring data confidentiality involves encrypting data and limiting access to authorized individuals only.
- **Integrity:** Maintaining data integrity requires mechanisms to prevent unauthorized alterations by securing BEAGLE's information systems against tampering.
- **Availability:** Reliable access to data is critical, necessitating robust and functional information services to prevent system failures.
- **Authenticity:** Verifying user identities through robust authentication systems, such as two-factor authentication, is essential for securing data transmission and system access.
- **Non-repudiation:** Implementing systems that record transactions to confirm that data sharing activities are undeniable by either party involved, ensuring accountability and traceability.

Each partner, along with any associated third parties, is responsible for upholding these principles throughout the project. Partners with their own data security policies will integrate these into BEAGLE's overall data protection strategy.

URV, serving as the Project Coordinator, will oversee data protection, ensuring compliance with internal policies, regional laws, and GDPR. The data will be safely stored in trusted repositories such as Zenodo and SocArXiv for long-term preservation and curation. COARA will facilitate the sharing of research datasets in a FAIR manner. This centralized coordination complements the individual data protection efforts of each partner.

¹ The 5 pillars of information security and how to manage them. (2022, July 18). Infnit-0 Resource Center. <https://resourcecenter.infnit-o.com/blog/the-5-pillars-of-information-security-and-how-to-managethem/>

5 ETHICAL AND LEGAL ASPECTS

The consortium confirms that the project will comply with national and EU legislation in accordance with the EU legal framework. Specifically, relevant national laws, transposed from the EU Data Protection Directive 95/46/EC (such as the Spanish Protection Act) will be followed.

The General Data Protection Regulation (Regulation (EU) 2016/679) (GDPR) is an EU law which entered into force in 2016 and, following a two-year transition period, became directly applicable law in all Member States of the EU on May 25, 2018, without requiring implementation by the EU Member States through national law.

Data protection in Spain is regulated by the Spanish Act of Data Protection (in Spanish, Ley Orgánica 15/1999 de Protección de Datos, LOPD, the transposition of the EU Directive 95/46/CE) and the Spanish Constitution (article 10 and 18.4).

The Belgian Data Protection Authority, the successor of the Belgian Privacy Commission, was established by the Belgian Federal Chamber of Representatives by the Act of December 3, 2017 ('DPA Act'). Several other laws have also been adapted to align them with the GDPR (e.g. Video Surveillance Act).

Potential ethics or legal issues that can impact data sharing include ensuring participant consent, protecting sensitive data, and compliance with GDPR and national laws. These issues will be addressed in the project's ethics deliverables and the ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA). The consortium will refer to the ethics deliverables and the ethics chapter in the DoA to ensure all ethical considerations are properly addressed.

6 ANNEX 1: DECLARATION OF CONSENT

Please tick all appropriate boxes and return duly signed before the workshop, events, interviews, surveys.

	I hereby declare that I am willing to take part in BEAGLE interview.
	I declare that I have been properly informed about the BEAGLE project and I understand the written and verbal explanations.
	I was given proper time to reflect on the participation request; I had the opportunity to make the necessary questions and I received satisfactory answers.
	I understand I will be asked if I object that a picture is being taken and I can choose not to appear.
	I authorise that pictures including me can be used in BEAGLE’s communication and dissemination action, namely in BEAGLE social media and website
	I authorise audio records and videos only to be used for analysing the data from the interview/workshop and further technical development, unless stated otherwise
	I authorise audio records and videos also to be used as learning and dissemination materials in the BEAGLE social media and website, as from its consortium partners.
	I know that information that I give in an interview or workshop will be analysed and summarised by my interviewer. I will have the right to review its final version, as well as its use for BEAGLE outcomes.
	I was informed that the data will only be stored five years after the ending of the project. after which it will be deleted and that I can access or change/delete it at any time.
	I understand that my name, or any information that may identify me personally, will only be displayed with my express consent.
	I understand I can withdraw my participation at any time, without having to give a reason and will have no penalties because of it.
	I would like to receive more information about the BEAGLE project receive the project newsletter to the following email address: _____

Please, select only one option.

	I allow to share my name, organisation, picture, audio or video record in the BEAGLE marketplace, social media and website, as well as in different reports and publications within the scope of this project.
	I do not allow my name, organisation, picture, audio or video record to be shared in the BEAGLE marketplace, social media and website

Participant

Name:

Date and signature:

Researcher informing the participant and collecting the consent

Name:

Date and signature: